

Reproducibility in GIScience: How We Can Leverage Reproducibility to Enliven Research Articles

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Paradoxically, as computational methods have been increasingly adopted in science, reproducibility has suffered. A Nature survey [1] revealed that over 70% of researchers failed to reproduce another's experiments, and more than half couldn't replicate their own work. In GIScience, reproducibility remains a challenge: a systematic assessment of AGILE conference papers found that over 80% lacked the data, code, or documentation necessary to support the reproduction of the research [3].

In response to these challenges, various solutions have emerged. Literate Programming Environments like Jupyter, Quarto, and RMarkdown enable researchers to combine code, data, and methods with a research narrative. Workflow management systems such as CWL and Kepler enable the modular composition of computational tools. Containerisation technologies such as Docker and Kubernetes support the creation of portable computational environments. Collectively these technologies have moved computational science toward more robust and reproducible research.

Despite these advances, opportunities remain to make reproducibility the default rather than an exception. Research artifacts such as code and data remain fragmented, and changes to these artifacts are not reflected in their associated article. LivePublication [2] tackles these limitations by interfacing research articles with in-situ computational experiments. As new data is processed, results generated, and methods modified, so too is the article. In this talk I demonstrate how we can take a GIScience workflow, such as monitoring and predicting coastal erosion, and interface it with a dynamic publication. The result is a publication container which must be reproducible, as the research article itself is an emergent property of executing the workflow.

References

- [1] Monya Baker. “1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility”. en. In: *Nature* 533.7604 (May 2016), pp. 452–454.
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